

Field reaction of upland rice lines to root-knot nematode infestation at Kok-Primeng Rubber Experiment Station, Narathiwat, Thailand.

Cross	Selection no.	Infestation ^a (%)	Reaction ^b
SPR72103-67-2/IR208-78	SPRLR77205-3-2-1-4	37	MR
SPT7220-13-13-1/RD5	BKNLR77003-PSL-65021	81	S
RD11/IR28	SPRLR5010-149-1-1	92	S
RD1/IR28	SSPRLR75001-60-1-2	81	S
RD7/IET2845/IR4215-4-3-1-1	SPRLR223-53-2-2	87	S
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-5-08	25	R
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-6-030	31	MR
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-12-072	44	MR
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-15-050	25	R
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-17-091	31	MR
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-12-072	25	R

^a Av of 4 replications. ^b R = 0-25% root galls, MR = 26-50%, MS = 51-75%, and S = 76-100%.

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Soil and Crop Management

Organic matter as a P source for azolla

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Azolla culture with lowland rice is drawing farmer interest in northeastern India. P is essential for rapid azolla growth, and P deficiency gives azolla a red-brown color. For best azolla growth, 8.8 kg P/ha must be applied, which is more than the total fertilizer applied by farmers in Assam. We studied organic matter supplements to provide P for azolla.

Cow dung and poultry litter, applied to equal 9 kg P/ha at 1- or 2-mo intervals were compared to 0 and 9 kg P applied at 1-mo intervals.

Results (see table) showed that azolla growth increased from Mar to May, then declined from Jun to Aug. In May, the interaction of application intervals and organic matter sources was significant. Azolla grew better with 2-mo applications of cow dung and poultry litter.

Results indicated that when organic matter is used as a P source it should be applied well ahead of azolla inoculation so soil microorganisms can break it down and make it available as an azolla nutrient. Applying 9 kg P/ha as single superphosphate significantly increased azolla production. □

Azolla biomass production as affected by P application and 2 application intervals of cow dung and poultry litter, Assam, India.

Organic matter source	Application intervals (mo)	P as SSP ^a (kg/ha)	Azolla biomass production (t/ha)							
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug
No organic matter	—	—	6.0	6.7	15.5	21.2	23.7	14.9	14.4	13.2
No organic matter	—	9	7.6	8.5	19.5	28.0	33.5	18.0	17.5	17.3
Cow dung	1	—	6.0	7.5	17.6	27.1	28.5	16.9	15.0	17.5
Cow dung	1	9	6.9	8.4	22.7	29.2	31.0	21.7	17.2	19.7
Poultry litter	1	—	5.6	8.1	16.6	23.7	24.0	18.4	17.2	20.7
Poultry litter	1	9	6.5	7.2	21.2	28.2	25.7	19.9	17.9	19.9
No organic matter	—	—	6.2	7.2	15.9	20.9	23.0	16.8	16.7	15.5
No organic matter	—	9	7.4	7.2	20.9	29.5	28.2	19.0	17.0	15.7
Cow dung	2	—	5.7	6.1	18.6	23.7	32.5	16.9	15.7	14.9
Cow dung	2	9	5.1	9.5	23.3	32.1	36.2	20.8	19.8	18.9
Poultrylitter	2	—	4.7	8.2	16.6	27.6	29.0	17.9	14.2	14.2
Poultrylitter	2	9	7.0	8.7	22.1	30.1	39.5	20.8	19.1	17.4
Mean	—	—	6.2	7.8	19.2	26.8	29.2	18.5	16.8	17.1
		SEm (P)	0.3	0.3	0.7	0.8	0.5	0.7	0.6	0.8
		CD (0.05)	0.8	ns	2.1	2.5	4.4	2.1	1.6	ns
		SEm (F × C)	0.4	0.6	1.3	1.5	2.6	1.3	1.0	1.5
		CD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns	7.7	ns	ns	ns

^a Single super phosphate.

Nitrogen requirement and spacing for late-transplanted, photoperiod-sensitive, tall indica rice

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In parts of Bihar, early Jul floods wash out lowland rice. Farmers retransplant in Aug with old seedlings of tall,

photoperiod-sensitive indicas. Sometimes, labor shortages also delay transplanting. We sought to identify a suitable rate and time of N application and spacing for Janaki, a new photoperiod-sensitive variety suitable for poorly drained lowlands. A field trial was conducted at RAU Research Farm in 1981 kharif.

The experiment was in a split-plot design with three replications. Janaki was planted in four spacings and with six times and rates of N application (see